

Attitude of Benin Residents to Broadcast Media Waste Recycling Campaigns in Edo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was carried out to examine the extent to which Benin City residents are exposed to broadcast campaigns on waste recycling, identify the communication strategies used, investigate residents' perception of the message conveyed, determine the factors influencing attitudes towards waste recycling and evaluate the effectiveness of the campaigns. Anchored on the social judgement theory and source credibility theory, the study employed survey research design, utilising questionnaire as the instrument of data collection. The findings revealed that a significant 79.8% of residents are exposed to waste recycling campaigns carried out by ITV and NTA. However, while residents perceive the messages as clear and important, their influence on attitudes towards recycling is mixed. Factors such as personal beliefs, availability of recycling facilities and social norms were found to influence attitudes towards waste recycling. The study concluded that although broadcast media campaigns increased awareness, the extent of their effectiveness in driving actual recycling behaviours was low. Consequently, the study recommended that the government invest in expanding recycling infrastructure, community leaders organise workshops and events, schools incorporate environmental education, and local businesses offer incentives for recycling participation.

Keywords: Attitude, Broadcast Media, Broadcast Campaign, Waste Recycling

Introduction

Developing countries all over the world, including Nigeria, have been challenged to manage solid waste effectively by developing efficiency in collection, recycling, treatment and disposal mechanism. It is a problem recognised by all nations at the 1992 conference on Environment and Development and considered a major barrier in the lane towards sustainability of the environment (Ifegbesan, 2009). After the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro in January 1992, countries started to formally adopt Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) policies undated legislature, strategies and guideline that needed information dissemination and public consultation on project for which development permits were required. Managing the exponential growth of waste is cost-intensive but indeed, necessary to contain the adverse effects of environmental hazards, if left unmanaged, would lead to pollution and natural disasters. Abushammala *et al* (2011) and Lapinski & Rimal (2005) pointed out that waste increases in tandem with population growth. Population growth and industrial revolution are often kept close to parallel with one another and they fueled the throwaway

culture indirectly, were consumer demands for newer and better things. Significantly, broadcast media campaign can totally influence waste recycling by raising public awareness about importance of recycling programmes, ultimately leading to increased recycling rates within a community. This is achieved through the power of mass communication to shape public opinion and behaviour towards environmental sustainability.

On this note, the ability for broadcast media to influence and persuade every member of the society towards embracing the culture of proper disposal and recycling of waste will not only protect the society from diseases and blockage of our drainage system, but will increase the economic standard. However, the impact of broadcast media with its audio-visual power can definitely bring about attitude change toward waste recycling in our society. In general wielding the authority to mold perceptions, beliefs and behaviours, both at an individual and societal level.

The improper disposal of waste, particularly non-biodegradable waste, has become a significant environmental concern in Nigeria, with the country's large population of approximately 235,466,621 people (as of January 28, 2025, based on Worldometer's elaboration of the latest United Nations data) contributing to the generation of vast amounts of waste. Despite efforts by governments and environmentalists to promote waste recycling and proper waste disposal practices, many residents in Benin City, Edo State, continue to disregard these initiatives. The issue of improper waste disposal is the bedrock to environmental pollution and hazard, which in turn leads to blockage in our drainages, resulting to flooding during the raining season. When biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste are not properly sorted and disposed, it provides the atmosphere for the spread of different diseases. However, there is a lack of understanding about the attitude of Benin city residents towards broadcast media recycling campaigns, which are critical in promoting behavioural change and encouraging sustainable waste management practices for the purpose of environmental friendliness. This is the thrust of the study

Objective of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which Benin City residents are exposed to broadcast media campaigns on the importance of waste recycling.
2. Find out the broadcast channel through which Benin city residents are mostly exposed to waste disposal and recycling.
3. Examine the perception of Benin residents toward the message conveyed in the broadcast media campaign on waste recycling.
4. Ascertain the level of message consistency in the dissemination of campaigns on waste recycling
5. Evaluate the effectiveness of broadcast media campaigns in ensuring the adoption of waste recycling in Benin City.

Conceptualisation of Attitude

Attitude is a person's enduring predisposition to evaluate an object, person, group or issue favourably or unfavourably (Asemah, 2011). This predisposition is shaped by an

individual's beliefs, values and experiences, influencing their cognitive, affective and conative responses. In the context of waste management, an individual's attitude towards waste recycling is influenced by their evaluation of the benefits and costs of recycling. For instance, if an individual believes that recycling is beneficial to the environment, they are more likely to have a positive attitude towards waste recycling. Attitude can also be defined as a mental state that influences an individual's behaviour and decision-making processes. In the context of environmental conservation, an individual's attitude towards the environment plays a significant role in determining their willingness to engage in environmentally friendly practices. According to Asemah (2011), attitude is a crucial factor in shaping human behaviour, particularly in the context of mass communication. For example, if an individual has a positive attitude towards environmental conservation, they are more likely to participate in recycling programmes and reduce their waste output.

Broadcast Media

Broadcast media is the inclusion of different media that are used for communicating, transmitting and broadcasting to the public or masses. It uses a wide range of audio-visual materials as well as electronic or electro-magnetic media to share news, information, entertainment, among others, with the target audiences or general public. Broadcast media can be television news, audio production, video and print media production, television and radio programme. It provides the recorded content, digital and written content or live recording on radio, television, or any other means through satellite signals.

Asemah (2011) asserts that broadcasting is the transmission of signals through space, using radio frequencies, to deliver audio, visual or both types of content to the general public. This encompasses the use of electronic media such as radio, television and the internet to reach a wide and diverse audience. This implies that broadcasting serves as a vital tool for information dissemination, education and entertainment, playing a significant role in shaping public perception and societal development. Broadcasting is essential in promoting recycling behaviour by informing, educating and entertaining the masses on various issues regarding waste collection, sorting, disposal and how to go about recyclable waste materials, thereby contributing to national growth and development.

Understanding Broadcast Media Campaign

Broadcast media campaigns can be defined as a planned and coordinated series of communication activities designed to achieve a specific goal or objective. These campaigns use various forms of media, such as television, radio and social media to reach a wide audience and convey a message. As asserted by Nwaoboli, Ogunyemi & Ezegwu (2023), these campaigns are orchestrated efforts to promote a distinct message, product, service or cause to a defined audience through a range of media channels. The primary goals include creating awareness, generating interest and shaping audience behaviour or perception. Nwaoboli (2022) emphasises that broadcast media campaigns typically encompass a series of coordinated activities across various channels, chosen based on the

target audience, campaign objectives, budget and available resources. Commonly utilised broadcast media channels in campaigns include television, radio, social media platforms, mobile apps, email marketing and more (Ovie & Nwaoboli, 2022; Asemah & Nwaoboli, 2022). One of the primary purposes of broadcast media campaigns is to advocate for a particular cause or issue. For instance, campaigns promoting waste recycling or environmental conservation are examples of Environmental campaign.

Waste Recycling for Sustainable Development

Waste recycling is a process of converting waste materials into new products to prevent waste of potentially useful materials, partly supplement the consumption of fresh raw materials, reduce energy usage (almost 70% less energy is required in recycling), reduce air pollution from incineration and water pollution from land filling by reducing the need for “conventional” waste disposal and lower greenhouse gas emissions. The idea or philosophy of waste recycling is to bring into the fore the idea of re-using their sources or materials that has been used for renewed use again.

Recycling is a crucial aspect of sustainable development, promoting resource conservation, pollution reduction and planet preservation (Abimbola *et al* 2023; Aigbefoh, 2021; Abah & Okoduwa, 2021). Recycling helps in lowering the demand for extracting resources; thus, preserving natural resources such as forests, minerals and water. The importance of recycling is increasingly recognised every single day around the world and its relationship with sustainability is becoming more apparent. Sustainability and recycling are two highly linked subjects that are closely intertwined (Aigbefoh, 2021). Recycling is necessary to ensure sustainable development goals, and it is a vital component of effective waste management solutions. However, various significant obstacles exist to achieving effective waste management and sustainable development in Nigeria today (Adewole, 2009; Abimbola *et al* 2023). These challenges include the rise in population, the waste disposal practices of individuals, the disposition of waste collectors and disposal personnel and the need for appropriate equipment.

The importance of adopting recycling into our daily routines cannot be emphasised enough, as it has a direct impact on both our personal welfare and the overall health of the environment (Ogunleye, 2020). Recycling is crucial in our everyday life for several reasons. First, it helps in the preservation of valuable natural resources like minerals, water and forests by decreasing the need for extracting raw materials (Ezeudu, 2022). For instance, recycling paper reduces the number of trees cut down for paper production, preserving forests and the habitats they provide for wildlife. Furthermore, recycling is practically more energy-efficient than producing new materials from scratch (Adeosun, 2021).

Effective Waste Management Communication Strategies

Effective communication is foundational to a healthy society or community. People communicate in various ways and understanding how and when to use each type of communication can benefit once ability to communicate effectively. Communication according to Asemah (2011) and Asemah (2020) is the process of sharing information, ideas and attitude. This connotes that when communication is effectively shared using the right strategies, it has all tendency to influence ideas and change attitude. More so,

effective waste management communication refers to the process of conveying information, ideas and messages to various stakeholders, including policymakers, waste generators and waste management professionals, to promote proper waste management practices, behaviours and policies. It can also be said to be a planned approach or strategy to conveying messages about the need for proper waste management to the members of the society using different channels of communication. For effective reception to such message, it is very important for the media to take into consideration the following strategies before crafting a campaign message, this includes: understanding the audience, communication channel and timing.

Broadcast Media and Attitude Change

The main objective of any broadcast programme under whatever genre, is to influence the audience positively through the impartation of the right information, education or entertainment that would bring out the best in the audience members in line with societal norms and values (Bittner, 1989). It is in a bid to achieve these tasks that broadcast media have developed a strategy for making their messages more effective and influential using a combination of education and entertainment known as “entertainment-education” or a fusion of information with entertainment referred to as “infotainment.” However, broadcast stations are capable of transmitting signals within Edo States and beyond, as such, capable of “shaping social norms and values, influence peoples decisions in manners that promote recycling culture across the state” (Nwabueze, 2007, pp. 49). Communication plays a central role in shaping our understanding of the natural world and the role of humans therein. Okunna (2002) believes that communication facilitates positive change to the target audience in terms of improving their living conditions. This is possible when there is “effective mobilisation aimed at creating favourable attitudes and behaviours among the people for whom a development project is being executed” (Okunna, 2002:300). In the same vein, McQuail (2010) argues that the media could be a potent force for public enlightenment and popular education. Communication is also the terrain where diverse points of view are negotiated. The broadcast media, for example, are central arena for amplifying environmental issues such as How to properly dispose waste, and can influence the course of policy and attitudinal change

Empirical Review

Idamah (2022) conducted a study on the influence of broadcast media enlightenment campaigns on solid waste management in South-South Nigeria. The study was guided by the theory of planned behaviour and value change theory. Survey research and content analysis methods were adopted in his study, The rationale behind the study was to determine the relationship between public awareness of the broadcast media and attitudinal change towards solid waste management enlightenment campaigns in south-south Nigeria. The main finding of the study was hinged on the fact that broadcast media with its features of pictures and sound are capable of influencing or inducing responsible environmental behaviour if there are regular enlightenment campaigns on environmental issues. Idamah’s study shares similarities with this present study in the aspect of utilising broadcast media campaign to drive home the needed change in the society.

Abdulazeez, Asemah & Ekhareafu (2024) examined the awareness and perception of media campaign on environmental sustainability in Benin City, Nigeria. Their study adopted a quantitative research design, utilising questionnaire as the method of data collection. The main finding of their study indicated that there is a limited awareness about the knowledge of environmental sustainability, bordering on the need to leverage divers' communication channel (television/new media) backed up with transparency, accuracy and relevance in the campaign message. Abdulazeez *et al's* study. concentrated on awareness, perception and environmental sustainability; whereas, this study explored how waste recycling media campaign can influence the resident of Benin city for the purpose of adoption and behavioural change.

Theoretical Framework

Social Judgement Theory

The social judgement theory is a theoretical framework that explains how people evaluate and respond to persuasive messages based on their existing attitudes and values. The theory has several tenets that underpin its framework. First, the theory suggests that people's attitudes and values serve as anchors for evaluating messages (Johnson & Boynton, 2022). This means that individuals tend to evaluate messages based on how well they align with their existing attitudes and values. Second, the theory posits that people engage in ego-involvement, where they evaluate messages based on their personal relevance and importance (Umeh & Adeosun, 2021).

Source Credibility Theory

The source credibility theory is a theoretical framework that explains how the credibility of a source influences the effectiveness of a persuasive message. Studies have applied the theory in various contexts, including environmental behaviour and sustainability. For instance, a study by Okoro & Ezeudu (2023) found that source credibility was a significant predictor of attitudes towards waste recycling among young adults in Nigeria. The study revealed that sources that were perceived as credible and trustworthy were more effective in promoting positive attitudes towards waste recycling. The theory has several tenets that underpin its framework. First, the theory suggests that expertise is a critical factor in determining source credibility (Hovland & Weiss, 1951). Second, the theory posits that trustworthiness is also essential for source credibility, as people are more likely to trust sources that are perceived as honest and unbiased (Okoro & Ezeudu, 2023). It is on this note that this theory is relevant to this study.

Methodology

This study employed survey research design. Survey research design is a quantitative approach that involves collecting data from a sample of participants through self-report measures, allowing researchers to capture attitudes, behaviours and opinions of a population. This design was chosen because it enabled the collection of data from a large sample via the distribution of questionnaire, providing a representative view of the study population. It also facilitated the analysis of relationships between variables and allowed

for generalisability of findings to the larger population. The population of this study is 1,904,631. This figure is based on the population projection provided by World Population Statistics, 2023 as population of Benin City. This population served as the target group for the research, allowing for a comprehensive examination of the research objectives within the specific context of Benin City. The sample size for this study was 384. Krejcie and Morgan formula with 95% confidence level ($Z = 1.96$) and a margin of error of 5% (expressed as a decimal, 0.05) was used to calculate the survey sample size. Using the formula: $n = (Z^2 \cdot p \cdot q) / (E^2)$ Where: n = required sample size Z = Z-score corresponding to the desired confidence level p = estimated proportion of the population $q = 1 - p$ (complement of p) E = margin of error Inputting these figures $n = (1.96^2 \cdot 0.5 \cdot 0.5) / (0.05^2)$ $n = (3.8416 \cdot 0.25) / 0.0025$ $n = 0.9604 / 0.0025$ $n \approx 384$. Considering the size of the population, the researcher employed a multi-stage sampling technique to select respondents. The data collection instrument employed in this study is the questionnaire. Additionally, the utilisation of secondary sources, including the internet, journals, articles, and textbooks, was employed to meticulously gather data for the investigation.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Responses on the Extent of Exposure to Broadcast Media Campaigns on Waste Recycling in Benin City

Response Option	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very high	75	19.7
High	110	28.9
Can't tell	15	3.9
Low	85	22.3
Very low	96	25.2
Total	381	100

The data in table 3 indicate that a significant proportion of respondents have a high exposure to broadcast media campaigns regarding waste recycling. This shows that Benin residents are well exposed to the campaign.

Table 2: Channels of Exposure to Waste Recycling Campaigns

Channel	Frequency	Percentage (%)
NTA	95	24.9
ITV/Radio	111	29.1
Silverbird Television	40	10.5
Raypower FM	25	6.6
EBS Television/Radio	45	11.8
Bronze FM	46	12.1
Others	19	4.9
Total	381	100

Table 2 reveals that ITV/Radio and NTA are the most prevalent channel for exposure to waste recycling campaigns.

Table 3: Responses on the Perception of the Effectiveness of the Broadcast Campaigns

Response Option	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very effective	55	14.4
Effective	85	22.3
Can't tell	15	3.9
Low	90	23.6
Very low	136	35.7
Total	381	100

The data in the above indicate that the effectiveness of the campaign is low. This is based on the fact that majority of the respondents answered in that direction (59.3%)

Table 4: Consistency Level of Broadcast Media Campaigns lead to Increase in Waste Recycling Behaviours

Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly agree	130	34.1
Agree	100	26.3
Neutral	90	23.6
Disagree	46	12.1
Strongly disagree	15	3.9
Total	381	100

Table 4 showed that a good number of the respondents strongly agreed that the consistency level of broadcast media campaigns can result to increase in recycling behaviour.

Table 5: Responses on the Extent to which the Broadcast Media Campaigns on waste Recycling Influenced the Attitude of Benin Residents Towards Waste Disposal

Response Option	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Very high	70	18.4
High	100	26.3
Can't tell	30	7.9
Low	90	23.6
Very low	91	23.8
Total	381	100

The data in the table showed that notable proportion of the respondents agreed that the campaigns have had a significant impact.

Discussion of Findings

The findings showed that Benin City residents are highly exposed to broadcast campaigns on waste recycling. The data presented in table 1 clearly illustrates this level of exposure (79.8%). This overwhelming response suggests that awareness initiatives surrounding waste recycling have effectively reached a substantial portion of the population, which is

crucial for fostering both knowledge and practical engagement with waste management practices.

The findings showed that the respondents are mostly exposed to information on proper waste disposal and recycling on ITV/Radio and NTA Benin. The significance of mass media in shaping public opinion cannot be overstated; hence Asemah (2011) argues that effective communication through mass media is vital for raising awareness and promoting behavioural change. The findings further showed that broadcast media campaigns increase awareness of waste recycling. This suggests that broadcast media serve as an effective tool for raising awareness and informing the public about the importance of recycling practices. As highlighted by Asemah (2011), effective communication through mass media is vital for reaching a broad audience. However, the findings showed that the campaign is less effective.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study revealed critical insights into the efficacy of broadcast media campaigns aimed at promoting waste recycling. The findings indicate a high level of exposure to these campaigns, with 79.8% of residents acknowledging their presence. This substantial awareness is crucial for fostering a culture of recycling and enhancing public engagement with waste management practices. However, while the clarity and perceived importance of the messages are commendable, their influence on attitudes towards recycling is not uniformly positive, suggesting that further refinement of campaign strategies is needed. Thus, the government should invest in expanding recycling infrastructure and facilities in Benin City to remove barriers to participation and ensure that residents have accessible options for recycling. This could include establishing more recycling bins and collection points across the city. Also, broadcast media houses should develop and implement more engaging and relatable content for social media platforms to enhance the effectiveness of their campaigns. Community leaders, non-governmental organisations, schools and universities should organise workshops and community events that promote waste recycling and educate residents on its importance.

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